

THE ROLE OF INTERNET MARKETING AND ADVERTISING IN ENTERPRISES

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ABSTRACT

This article describes the role of marketing systems that are becoming popular nowadays in the business and the impact of Internet marketing on the economy of enterprises.

During the transformation of the traditional economy to the digital economy, the role of Internet marketing in modern marketing will increase. It is becoming an important part of the marketing policy of companies that want to run a successful business. Thanks to modern information and communication technologies (ICT), Internet marketing remains an important tool for promoting a company's business on the Internet. Internet marketing has allowed companies to attract potential customers much faster and more than traditional marketing. Thanks to the global network of the Internet, companies have the opportunity to promote their goods and services around the globe at any time, without breaks or holidays, 365/7/24. Compared to traditional marketing, promotion of goods or services with the

help of Internet marketing costs typical of traditional marketing - delivery of promotional mailings, payment for advertising on billboards, advertising brochures, costs for publication of newsletters or is more effective due to Therefore, companies have the opportunity to earn more. Choosing the right Internet marketing strategy by the company is an important component that helps companies to successfully advertise and sell their goods and services, as well as organize feedback with customers. Here are some of the advantages of Internet marketing over traditional marketing:

1. Increasing company recognition. Thanks to the Internet, companies create their own recognition in the network through their

websites, social networks, advertising, etc. With the right strategy of the company to promote itself on the network, millions of users around the world can learn about the company in a short time;

2. Study the market more carefully. There are many resources and tools on the Internet that allow company marketers to collect detailed information about consumers and track their activities and preferences;

3. Provide prompt feedback. With the help of social networks, specialized sites, rating or expert research and forums, consumers have the opportunity to rate the company's product or service. Customers can also connect directly to organizations and vice versa. By staying in touch with customers through follow-up emails, personalized offers and thank-you notes, organizations can build relationships and define a sense of commonality around their brand.

An important task of Internet marketing is to influence the specific target audience, or targeting. To do this, the advertising material links to the resource are placed in such areas, which are able to provide a more complete coverage of the target audience for each specific type of product or service. By studying the audience, similar groups are divided according to applications, and a specific advertising tool is used for each of them. If the goal of Internet marketing is to promote sites, type and type of goods or services being advertised, depending on the audience a set of selected actions is applied. The main methods of Internet marketing are ensuring brand recognition and distinguishing it from competitors, placement of advertising materials on appropriate platforms according to effectiveness, targeting. Well-thought-out

Internet marketing is the formation of goals, setting tasks and consistently following all planned stages. . Companies that actively use the Internet in their activities can be divided into the following categories:

1. From selling your goods or services via the Internet companies seeking additional income. To them who gives information about goods or services on the network, own includes companies that receive orders for goods or services;
2. Their expenses in promoting their goods or services to reduce and reduce the time of the transaction aspiring companies;
3. To improve one's image in the network, long-term relations in order to establish stable relations with customers companies seeking to create.

Companies that use the opportunities of the global network receive income from the sale of their goods or services, paid advertising, commissions for financial transactions, cloud services, etc. Let's look at the most successful Internet companies in the world:

Amazon company

Created in 1994 by Joseph Bezos. Amazon is one of the largest companies in the world that sell various goods and services through the Internet. It is a leader in the field of selling mass market goods through the Internet. A unique aspect of Amazon's activity is that every customer can express their opinion and evaluate the purchased goods. This is an incentive for the company to help the customer choose a quality product that ranks high on the list of best products. At the same time, feedback helps companies remove low-quality or substandard products when a customer leaves a negative rating on a product. As of

July 2020, Amazon's capitalization exceeded \$1.5 trillion.

Alphabet Inc. Kompaniyasi (Google)

The company is one of the world leaders in the field of digital technologies. The main activity of the company is the development of innovative information search technologies, advertising technologies and cloud computing on the Internet. Google has developed and supports a number of Internet services and products - Gmail, YouTube, Google Maps, Google Docs, Google Earth and many others. As of January 2020, Amazon's capitalization exceeded \$1 trillion

Facebook, Inc. Company

Founded by Mark Zuckerberg in 2004, Facebook is one of the largest Internet companies in the world. Facebook is the largest social network for promoting the products or services of companies. Facebook allows users to leave feedback as followers can comment on posts, rate

brand pages for others to see. Facebook can link to a product page on Twitter and send event reminders. As of 2021, the company's market capitalization was \$767.162 billion.

Alibaba commerce

Alibaba Group, an e-commerce and web portal company, was founded in Hangzhou in 1999 by Ma Yun, a Chinese businessman known as Jack Ma. Today, Alibaba Group is the largest e-commerce platform owned by the Chinese corporation Alibaba Group. Alibaba Group's market capitalization at the beginning of 2021 was \$728.262 billion.

In conclusion, the importance of Internet marketing for business is that it is more flexible and easier for business to grow, and it gives results much faster than traditional marketing. But most importantly, it's a wide selection of tools that allow entrepreneurs to find the best ways to run their business successfully.

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